

REVIEW

Environment

Assessment of soil erosion and sedimentation dynamics in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, Ethiopia

Degefu Dogiso¹

¹Agricultural Engineering Department, Institute of Technology, Hawassa University, Hawassa, Ethiopia

²Environmental Science/Climate Change Department, Institute of Technology, Hawassa University, Hawassa, Ethiopia

Correspondence

Degefu Dogiso, Agricultural Engineering, Institute of Technology, Hawassa University, P.O. Box 05, Hawassa, Ethiopia.
Email: ddegsw@yahoo.com

Assigned to Associate Editor Larry Cihacek

Abstract

Soil erosion and sedimentation are global issues threatening livelihoods and development, including in the Ethiopian Rift Valley Lakes Basin (RVLB). Despite several studies conducted at the watershed and subbasin levels in the basin, there is a lack of an organized review. This review synthesizes findings from 32 studies (2008–2023) to assess soil erosion and sedimentation rates, causes, and impacts in the RVLB. Key findings indicate that land use changes, such as converting vegetation and woodlands into cultivation and settlements, are the primary drivers of soil loss, with additional factors including steep slopes, poor conservation practices, and high rainfall. The mean annual soil loss rate in the basin is 28.44 t/ha/year, surpassing the national average of 16.5 t/ha/year and the RVLB average of 15.8 t/ha/year. Methodologies mainly rely on the Universal Soil Loss Equation and its revised version, Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation, alongside tools such as Soil and Water Assessment Tool, Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs—Sediment Delivery Ratio, object-based image analysis, and field measurements. The impacts include severe effects on crop production, hydrological efficiency, and lake sedimentation. Research gaps highlight methodological inconsistencies, limited studies on direct economic impacts, underrepresented gully erosion dynamics, and a lack of high-resolution data. Future research should focus on integrating high-resolution datasets, employing advanced geographic information system and machine learning techniques, and conducting socioeconomic impact studies. Addressing these areas is crucial for developing sustainable soil and water conservation strategies in the RVLB.

Plain Language Summary

The Rift Valley Lakes Basin (RVLB) in Ethiopia faces severe soil erosion driven by land use changes, steep slopes, poor conservation practices, and high rainfall. The mean annual soil loss rate is 28.44 t/ha/year, significantly exceeding both the

Abbreviations: DEM, digital elevation model; FM, field measurements; GIS, geographic information system; InVEST-SDR, Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs—Sediment Delivery Ratio; NDVI, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index; OBIA, object-based image analysis; RUSLE, Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation; RVLB, Rift Valley Lakes Basin; SWAT, Soil and Water Assessment Tool; USLE, Universal Soil Loss Equation.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2025 The Author(s). *Agrosystems, Geosciences & Environment* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC on behalf of Crop Science Society of America and American Society of Agronomy.

national average of 16.5 t/ha/year and the RVLB average of 15.8 t/ha/year. This erosion adversely affects crop productivity, hydrological systems, and lake sedimentation, leading to rising lake levels and the disappearance of smaller water bodies like Cheleleka. Assessment methodologies, including USLE, RUSLE, SWAT, and InVEST-SDR, reveal inconsistencies in input parameters, reducing reliability. Research gaps include a lack of high-resolution data, limited exploration of socio-economic impacts, and insufficient focus on gully erosion. To address these challenges, there is a need for advanced modeling techniques, integrated datasets, and targeted conservation strategies to ensure sustainable management of the basin's soil and water resources.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Soil erosion involves the removal, transport, and deposition of soil by facilitators such as rainfall, runoff, wind, and gravity (Aksoy et al., 2019; Boakye et al., 2020; Gadisa & Midega, 2021; Panagos et al., 2015; Sanogo et al., 2021). Sediment yield, on the other hand, refers to the amount of sediment reaching a watershed's outlet (Vigiak et al., 2012). These processes are caused by factors that affect soil erosion, including land use and cover changes, slope length, climate change, and soil erodibility (Gelagay & Minale, 2016).

Soil degradation is a complex process involving physical, chemical, and biological factors that reduce soil quality and its ability to support life. Healthy soils are rich in organic matter, and biodiversity, and have a balanced nutrient profile. Besides erosion, soil can be degraded through chemical contamination, loss of biodiversity, and physical compaction, often exacerbated by human activities (Bhattacharyya et al., 2015; Mamedov & Levy, 2019; Onet et al., 2019).

Soil erosion, a severe form of land resource depletion triggered by anthropogenic activities, is responsible for over 80% of cultivated land deterioration worldwide (Rodrigo Comino et al., 2015). Likewise, land deterioration has reduced crop yield in 23% of the global land area, impacting 3.2 billion people (Pandit et al., 2018). Similarly, 77% of Sub-Saharan Africa experiences 75 billion tonnes of annual soil erosion from farming (FAO, 2015). Moreover, 70%–90% of land degradation is caused by soil erosion, which is a significant global issue (Chalise et al., 2018). Soil erosion accounts for more than two-thirds of the degradation of agricultural land in Africa (Tully et al., 2015). Similarly, land deterioration has reduced crop yield in 23% of the global land area, impacting 3.2 billion people (Pandit et al., 2018).

Ethiopia's highlands are among the most highly degraded regions in sub-Saharan Africa, with 27 million ha of land deteriorating beyond rehabilitation capacity (Fenta et al., 2020). Reports by Hurni (1988) and FAO (1986) indicate that the Ethiopian highlands face yearly soil losses of 1.5×10^9 tonnes

and 1.9×10^9 tonnes, respectively, with mean soil loss rates of 42 t/ha/year for arable land, 5 t/ha/year for woodland and shrubland, and 1 t/ha/year for forest land, whereas the national average is 12 t/ha/year (Hurni, 1988).

Moreover, in Ethiopia, soil erosion by water triggers the highest annual soil loss rate of 16.5 t/ha/year, whereas the Rift Valley Lakes Basin (RVLB) encounters a rate of 15.8 t/ha/year (Fenta et al., 2021). Furthermore, soil erosion in arid and semiarid areas leads to the loss of productive topsoil, diminished crop yields, and reduced reservoir storage volumes for irrigation, livestock, and drinking water supplies (Aga, Chane, et al., 2018). Soil erosion in Ethiopia costs \$1 billion in earnings and causes an average of 42 t/ha/year of farmland soil loss yearly (Kebede et al., 2021).

In the RVLB, despite numerous studies conducted at watershed and subbasin levels, there is a lack of systematic review of the studies. Additionally, the fragmented nature of the studies makes it difficult to understand the rate, cause, impacts, and methods used to estimate soil loss and sedimentation. Hence, this paper focused to review thoroughly the present knowledge, changes, and main causes inducing soil erosion and sedimentation dynamics in the RVLB, Ethiopia, with an emphasis on (1) reviewing existing scholarly works on soil erosion rates and sediment dynamics, (2) recognizing the foremost causes and effects of soil erosion and sedimentation in the basin, and (3) presenting directions for forthcoming studies and viable soil conservation approaches to tackle soil erosion and sedimentation problems in the RVLB.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Location of the basin

The RVLB is one of the 12 major river basins in Ethiopia. It is a graben geological structure, covering 55,050 km² (Ayalew et al., 2023). It is hydrologically very different from other basins because it does not contain a major river. Most

basins are defined by their main river, but the RVLB is a series of lakes, some of which are connected, and all of the connected systems are terminal (MoWE, 2009). Its northern boundary is near Addis Ababa and runs south to the Kenyan border. The basin has four primary subbasins: Abaya-Chamo, Ziway-Shala, Lake Hawassa, and Chew Bahir; each with its lake system. It contains seven different lakes, including Lake Ziway, Langano, Abijata, Shalla, Hawassa, Abaya, and Chamo. The basin is predominantly composed of eutric fluvisols, which cover 12.59%, and chromic vertisols, with coverage of 10.92%. The soils with the least coverage are dystic regosols at 0.01% and gypsic yermosols at 0.03%. In the basin, the dominant land use and cover type is cropland, accounting for 45.53% of the area, whereas the least land use and cover type is sparse vegetation, comprising only 0.01% (Figure 1). Its elevation ranges from 500 to 3000 m a.s.l (Elias et al., 2019). Its geographic location lies between 4°22'44"–8°25'51" N latitude and 36°30'4"–39°19'35" E longitude.

2.2 | Literature collection methods

The study explored different databases to find literature on soil erosion and sediment yield in the RVLB basin. We downloaded 39 publications from 2008 to 2023, focusing on soil erosion assessment, modeling, factors, sediment yield, and drivers. Thirty-two articles were filtered based on criteria such as studies within the RVLB, high relevance to the title, clear methods, and publication in peer-reviewed journals.

Out of the 32 studies, 20 were conducted to estimate soil erosion due to sheet, rill, and inter-rill erosion using the USLE, RUSLE, and InVEST-SDR (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs—Sediment Delivery Ratio) models. Four studies estimated soil erosion due to gully erosion. Three studies used field measurements (FM), one study used object-based image analysis (OBIA) to analyze sedimentation by gully erosion, and eight studies estimated sediment yield using the SWAT model (Figure 2).

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Causes of soil erosion and sedimentation in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin

The studies concluded different causes for soil erosion and sedimentation in the basin. For instance, the majority of studies concluded that the causes of soil erosion in the watersheds and sub-watersheds are the expansion of cultivated lands (Guduru & Jilo, 2023; Tamire et al., 2022; Wolka et al., 2015; Wondrade, 2023), expansion of bare land (Guduru &

Core Ideas

- Land use changes and steep slopes drive severe soil erosion in Ethiopia's RVLB.
- RVLB's mean soil loss rate is 28.44 t/ha/year, exceeding national and basin averages, affecting sustainability.
- Soil erosion impacts crop yields, lake levels, and hydrological systems, threatening livelihoods and ecosystems.
- Models such as USLE (Universal Soil Loss Equation), RUSLE (Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation), and SWAT (Soil and Water Assessment Tool) assess soil erosion, but data inconsistencies hinder accurate predictions.
- High-resolution data, advanced techniques, and socioeconomic studies are needed for effective erosion control.

Jilo, 2023), steep slopes (Bekele & Gemi, 2021; Ketema & Dwarakish, 2020), poor conservation practices (Bekele & Gemi, 2021; Wolka et al., 2015), high rainfall (Desalegn et al., 2022), conversion of forest lands to agricultural lands (Meshesha et al., 2012), and soil characteristics (Tamire et al., 2022).

Other studies in different Ethiopian basins support the findings in the RVLB. For instance, a study in the Awash Basin by Mariye et al. (2022) in the Legedadi watershed, using historical Landsat images, revealed an increase in soil loss from 54.19 in 1997 to 66.21 t/ha/year in 2013 due to land use changes. Moreover, a study by Weldu and Edo (2020) conducted in the Wabi Shebele Basin, Erer subbasin, revealed an increase in soil loss due to the expansion of cultivated land, ranging from 75.85 in 2000 to 107.07 t/ha/year in 2018.

3.2 | Soil erosion and sedimentation rates in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin

3.2.1 | Soil erosion rate caused by sheet and rill erosion in the Lake Hawassa subbasin

In the Lake Hawassa subbasin, studies were conducted at both watershed and sub-watershed levels. Three studies were conducted at the subbasin level and three at the sub-watershed level. Their findings are described as follows:

The studies by Ketema and Dwarakish (2020) and Wolka et al. (2015) used the USLE and RUSLE models at the sub-watershed level, respectively. The first study found a soil loss estimation rate of 14.13 t/ha/year, within the tolerable rate

FIGURE 1 Location map of the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, showing the distribution of studies conducted within the basin and the various land use and land cover types.

in Ethiopia (2–18 t/ha/year; Hurni, 1985). The second study found a rate of 40.3 t/ha/year, above the mean annual soil loss rate. The country's and RVLB's mean annual soil loss rates are 16.5 and 15.8 t/ha/year, respectively (Fenta et al., 2021), which is a tolerable rate for Ethiopian conditions. Despite being conducted in the same watersheds, the soil loss rate estimations showed contradictory results, requiring further investigation into the cause of the reduction in soil erosion in the first study.

The other three studies at the Hawassa subbasin level were conducted using the USLE and InVEST-SDR models. According to Degife et al. (2021), using the InVEST-SDR model, the soil erosion rate in the watershed is 37 t/ha/year, which is twice the tolerable soil erosion rate in Ethiopia. The other two studies, by Ali and Hagos (2016) and Wondrade (2023), were conducted using the USLE model. For instance, the study by Wondrade (2023) used land use maps from different years, from 1975 to 2020. The soil loss rate increased from 25.16 in 1975 to 28.20 t/ha/year in 2020. In both periods, soil loss increased due to the decline of vegetation and the expansion of agricultural land.

In general, despite contradictory results, most studies suggest that, in the subbasin, the soil loss rate is greater than the tolerable soil loss rate of Ethiopia, as well as the mean soil loss rates in Ethiopia and the RVLB, which are 16.5 and 15.8 t/ha/year, respectively (Fenta et al., 2021). However, future studies need to investigate the contradictions in the results. We compared soil loss rates from various watersheds in the RVLB with Ethiopian and RVLB soil loss rates, as shown in Figure 3. The mean annual soil loss rate of Ethiopia is 16.5 and 15.8 t/ha/year in the RVLB (Fenta et al., 2021). Among the six studies, four reported an annual soil erosion rate exceeding both the national and basin averages.

3.2.2 | Soil erosion rate caused by sheet and rill erosion in the Abaya-Chamo subbasin

Studies on soil erosion in the Abaya-Chamo subbasin have shown significant increases over the past few decades. For instance, Tamire et al. (2022) found soil loss rates in the upper Bilate watershed of Ethiopia from 1991 to 2021 to be

FIGURE 2 Methods and models used to estimate sedimentation and soil erosion in the basin.

FIGURE 3 Comparison of soil erosion rates from various studies in the basin, including the mean soil loss rates for Ethiopia and the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, with a specific focus on the soil loss rate in the Lake Hawassa subbasin.

higher than Ethiopia's tolerable rate of 23 t/ha/year. Similarly, Nigusie and Dananto (2021) found a higher rate of 48.4 t/ha/year in the same watershed using the RUSLE model.

The other studies by Guduru and Jilo (2023) were conducted in the Gidabo watershed using the RUSLE model, estimating soil loss rates above the tolerable level. In the first study, the soil loss rate was 44.2 t/ha/year, whereas in the second study, the soil loss rates were 16.71, 19.98, and 36.26 t/ha/year in 1987, 2003, and 2021, respectively, all increasing linearly due to the expansion of bare lands and agricultural lands. Moreover, the study by Yirgu (2022) in the Upper Domba watershed, using the RUSLE model, revealed a soil erosion rate of 30.6 t/ha/year due to steep slopes.

In the study by Masha et al. (2021), using the RUSLE model in the Damota area districts with different years of land use images (2000 and 2020), the rate of soil loss decreased from 29.62 to 22.45 t/ha/year due to improved land cover and greenness. Despite this reduction, the soil loss in the watershed

remained above the tolerable soil loss rate. Another study by Bekele and Gemi (2021) in the Dijo watershed, using the USLE model, found that the soil loss rate in the sub-watershed is 2.2 t/ha/year, which is less than the Ethiopian tolerable soil loss rate.

Most studies indicate an increase in soil erosion in the Lakes Abaya-Chamo subbasins, exceeding the tolerable rate in Ethiopia. All studies report an increase in soil loss rates across various watersheds and sub-watersheds.

In general, despite contradictory results, most studies suggest that, in the subbasin, the soil loss rate is greater than the tolerable soil loss rate of Ethiopia, as well as the mean soil loss rates in Ethiopia and the RVLB, which are 16.5 and 15.8 t/ha/year, respectively (Fenta et al., 2021).

The reports of the studies agree with those in other basins and watersheds in Ethiopia. For instance, according to the study by Kidane et al. (2019) in the Guder sub-watershed, the watershed's average annual soil loss rates were 25.8, 28.7,

FIGURE 4 Comparison of soil erosion rates from various studies in the basin, including the mean soil loss rates for Ethiopia and the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, with a specific focus on the soil loss rate in the Abaya-Chamo subbasin.

and 30.3 t/ha/year for the 1973, 1995, and 2015 time periods, respectively. However, the soil loss rate is lower than in other neighboring basins, for example, Girma and Gebre (2020) reported a rate of 69 t/ha/year in the Omo-Gibe Basin, Ethiopia. We compared soil loss rates from various watersheds in the RVLB with Ethiopian and RVLB soil loss rates, as shown in Figure 4. The mean annual soil loss rate of Ethiopia is 16.5 t/ha/year, whereas it is 15.8 t/ha/year in the RVLB (Fenta et al., 2021). Therefore, the mean annual soil loss rate from all studies is higher than both the national average and the mean rate in the RVLB.

3.2.3 | Soil erosion rate caused by sheet and rill erosion in the Ziway-Shala subbasin

The Ziway-Shala subbasin includes Lake Ziway, Katar, Meki, and the central and northern parts of the watersheds. For instance, a study conducted by Meshesha et al. (2012) in the Central Rift Valley using the USLE model found a significant increase in soil erosion rates from 1973 to 2006, with annual rates of 31, 38, and 58 t/ha/year in 1973, 1985, and 2006, respectively. Similarly, another study by Mathewos et al. (2023) in the Matenchose sub-watershed, using the RUSLE model with different years of land use images (1991, 2003, and 2020), revealed an increase in soil erosion rates of 13, 18, and 21 t/ha/year in 1991, 2003, and 2020, respectively.

Another study by Woldeesenbet et al. (2020) in the Meki River watershed, using the RUSLE model for different years of land use images, shows that from 1987 to 2017, soil loss from *enset* growing was 30.5 t/ha/year, whereas non-*enset* growing zone had a rate of 31.905 t/ha/year. Although there was a decrease in the soil erosion rate, the soil loss rate remains above the tolerable level. Similarly, a study by Tadese et al. (2021) in the Sodo watershed found a soil loss rate of 35.28 t/ha/year using the RUSLE model.

Additionally, the study by Taye et al. (2023) in the Alage watershed, using the RUSLE model with two different years of land use data (1984 and 2016), reported an estimated soil loss rate of 24.3 and 38 t/ha/year, respectively, which is above the tolerable rate over the past 33 years. Furthermore, another study by Toma et al. (2023) in the Berta watershed, using the USLE model, estimated a soil loss rate of 27 t/ha/year due to the expansion of grassland and cropland, which is above the tolerable soil loss rate in Ethiopia.

All studies indicate that in the Ziway-Shala subbasin, the soil loss rate is above the tolerable rate. These studies only estimate soil loss due to sheet, rill, and inter-rill erosion, which is supported by other studies in the country. For instance, the study by Mengie et al. (2022) reported that in the Tashite watershed, the soil loss rate was 64.2 t/ha/year. Moreover, the study by Negese (2021) in the Chereti watershed reported a soil loss rate of 37.7 t/ha/year. Furthermore, the study in the Anjeb watershed in northwest Ethiopia by Tsegaye and Bharti (2021) reported that the annual soil loss rate was 17.3 t/ha/year.

We compared soil loss rates from various watersheds in the RVLB with Ethiopian and RVLB soil loss rates, as shown in Figure 5. The mean annual soil loss rate of Ethiopia is 16.5 and 15.8 t/ha/year in the RVLB (Fenta et al., 2021). Therefore, the mean annual soil loss rate from all studies is higher than both the national average and the mean rate in the RVLB.

3.2.4 | The rate of soil loss caused by gully erosion

Few studies have been conducted in the basin, especially in the Lake Hawassa subbasin. However, two studies were conducted in the small sub-watersheds of Umbulo, Tabota-Koromo, and Koromo-Danshe to estimate soil loss due to

FIGURE 5 Comparison of soil erosion rates from various studies in the basin, including the mean soil loss rates for Ethiopia and the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, with a specific focus on the soil loss rate in the Ziway-Shala subbasin.

gully erosion. From 1974 to 2006, the sub-watershed experienced a total soil loss of 590,431 m³, with a long-term gully erosion rate of 31 t/ha/year (Moges & Holden, 2008). Moreover, the study by Hassen and Bantider (2020) reported that the total soil loss in the watershed was 1,080,782.8 m³ due to anthropogenic and natural factors.

Other studies in the Lake Hawassa subbasin concerning gully erosion and sedimentation, such as the study by Gebre et al. (2023), used OBIA techniques. They reported that the sediment-loading rate from the watershed was in the range of 12.62–38.59 t/ha/year, and the sediment yield from the watershed was 8.83–27.02 t/ha/year. Furthermore, the study by Hoogenboom (2013) reported that the soil loss rate due to gully erosion was 22.05 t/ha/year.

The rate of soil loss in other Ethiopian watersheds and basins is higher than in the studies within the basin. For instance, the study by Zegeye et al. (2014) in the Debre-mewi watershed in the northwestern highlands of Ethiopia reported that the rate of soil loss by gully erosion was 127 t/ha/year. Moreover, the study by Yazie et al. (2020) in the Genbo Wonze watershed, also in the northwest highlands of Ethiopia, reported that the rate of soil loss by gully erosion was 62 t/ha/year.

3.2.5 | Sediment yield rate in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin

In the RVLB, sediment yield estimation studies were conducted at subbasin and watershed levels using InVEST-SDR, SWAT, and USLE. For instance, the study by Degife et al. (2021) in the Lake Hawassa watershed, using the InVEST-SDR model, revealed that the water bodies receive 226,690.3 tonnes of sediment annually, with a rate of 1.6 t/ha/year of exported sediment. This increased sediment yield not only

leads to the drying out of a small lake but also causes a rise in Lake Hawassa's water level.

According to another study by Tamire et al. (2022) in the upper Bilate watershed in the Lake Abaya-Chamo subbasin, using the InVEST-SDR model, the average annual exported sediment rate to the nearby water body was 3.62 t/ha/year. Furthermore, another study by Bekele (2023) in the Berta watershed in the Ziway-Shala subbasin, using the USLE model, found an annual sediment yield of 16,472.03 t/year, with a mean annual rate of 5.42 t/ha/year, primarily due to sheet, rill, and inter-rill erosion.

The studies in the Ethiopian River Basin also reported related results. For instance, the study in the Tekeze River Basin by Fenta et al. (2021) reported that due to sheet, rill, and inter-rill erosion, the mean annual sediment yield was 10 t/ha/year. Additionally, in the Omo-Gibe Basin, it was 7 t/ha/year and in the Abay Basin, it was also 7 t/ha/year. Moreover, Welde (2016) reported that at the Tekeze dam site, the mean sediment yield was 14 t/ha/year.

The SWAT model was used to estimate sediment yield in various subbasins in the RVLB, including the Ziway, Abiy-ata, Shala, and Langan subbasins. Although two studies were conducted in the Lake Abaya-Chamo subbasin, no study was conducted in the Lake Hawassa watershed using the SWAT model, which is advantageous as it estimates daily sediment yield. The sediment yield estimation studies by Ayele and Gebremariam (2020) in the Bilate watershed, using the SWAT model, found a sediment yield of 9.99 t/ha/year. This sediment yield indicates that much of the sediment is imported into Lake Abaya-Shala. Furthermore, the study by Dananto et al. (2022) in the Gidabo watershed, using the same model, found that the annual sediment yield was 2.92 million t/year. This indicates that much of the sediment is exported from the watershed and imported into the Gidabo irrigation dam and the Abaya-Chamo Lake.

FIGURE 6 Mean annual sedimentation rates of subbasins and watersheds from various studies in the Gidabo watershed.

In the study by Sime and Abebe (2022) in the Lake Katar watershed, Ziway-Shala subbasin, due to the expansion of cultivated land and soil characteristics, about 3784.14 t/ha/year of sediment yield was transported from the watershed and deposited in a lake located downstream. Furthermore, another study by Bunta and Abate (2021) in the Meki River watershed found that the rate of sediment yield to Lake Ziway was 13.12 t/ha/year. Additionally, the study by Gadissa et al. (2018) in the Central Rift Valley subbasin found that the sediment transported to Lake Ziway from the Meki River was 431.05 t/km² and from the Katar River, it was 322.82 t/km². In general, the sediment yield for subbasins and watersheds within the basin is presented in the graph in Figure 6.

3.3 | Soil erosion and sedimentation impacts in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin

3.3.1 | Impacts of soil erosion on crop production

The negative impact of soil erosion in the basin is clear. For instance, the study by Wolka et al. (2015) in the Cheleleka watershed and Lake Hawassa watershed concluded that the high rate of soil erosion threatens crop production, reduces land productivity, and affects the hydrological functioning of the watershed. Furthermore, another study by Tadesse and Tefera (2021) in the Sodo watershed, on the northern edge of the Lake Ziway–Meki River, concluded that soil erosion in the watershed poses chronic threats to the production of arable lands.

In another study by Moges and Holden (2008) in the Umbulo sub-watershed, Lake Hawassa subbasin, it was revealed that gully erosion leads to sediment deposition in the lower part of the sub-watershed, causing crop damage, backyard garden deposition, root rot, increased labor, and reduced plough life. Furthermore, in the watershed, due to the large

size of gullies, it is difficult to cooperate with neighbors, as people and animals can fall in and die, and access to land is made difficult.

The studies in other Ethiopian watersheds align with these findings. For instance, the study by Yazie et al. (2020) in the Genbo Wonze watershed in the northwest highlands of Ethiopia reported that, due to gully erosion, the *teff* grain yield (*Eragrostis tef* and *Erythrina abyssinica*) and animal forage were reduced by 24 t/ha/year. Furthermore, the study by Belay and Bewket (2012) reported that 46,265 m² of land was damaged due to gullies, of which 1401 m² was cropland, resulting in an annual crop yield reduction of 502 kg.

3.3.2 | Impacts of the sedimentation on the lakes and reservoirs

The Ethiopian RVLB, consisting of seven lakes (Elias et al., 2019), is susceptible to soil erosion risk (Bekele & Gemi, 2021). Studies have shown that increased sediment from the watershed, such as from the Hawassa watershed, has led to an increase in Lake Hawassa levels and dried out the small Cheleleka lake (Degife et al., 2021). Furthermore, sediment accumulation in the water bodies has been found in various watersheds, such as the Upper Bilate watershed, Lake Abaya-Chamo (Ayele & Gebremariam, 2020), Gidabo Irrigation Reservoir (Dananto et al., 2022), Meki River watershed (Bunta & Abate, 2021), and Katar River watershed (Sime & Abebe, 2022). Therefore, these findings highlight the need for effective management and mitigation strategies to address soil erosion risks.

The study by Gadissa et al. (2018) found that the sediment yield to Lake Ziway from the Meki River and Katar River is high, thereby reducing its life expectancy. Similarly, the study by Kalsido and Berhanu (2020) found average annual sediment yields of 3.59, 4.36, and 4.89 t/ha/year for three consecutive decadal periods from 1988 to 2018. Moreover, the

study by Gebre et al. (2023) found sediment loading rates ranging from 12.62 to 38.59 t/ha/year, indicating a 0.21% annual loss of the lake's storage capacity due to gully system sedimentation.

Studies from different parts of the globe confirm the impact of sedimentation in reservoirs and lakes. For instance, according to Palmieri et al. (2001), sedimentation is depleting reservoirs worldwide. Furthermore, Aga, Melesse, et al. (2018) reported that 2% of reservoirs' annual storage capacity was lost due to sedimentation. According to Moussa (2019), Sudan's Senar Reservoir has experienced significant storage loss due to sedimentation, losing 85% of its capacity in 85 years. Additionally, Ethiopia's Angereb Reservoir has lost 46% of its capacity in 19 years. Sudan's Khashm El-Girba Reservoir and Egypt's Aswan High Dam have also experienced significant storage losses due to sedimentation.

3.4 | Assessment approaches in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin

The review identifies six main methodologies to assess soil erosion and sedimentation in basins, with USLE and RUSLE being the most common. Other models include SWAT, InVEST-SDR, OBIA, and FM. Geographic information system (GIS)-based simulation modeling is valuable for evaluating alternatives and supporting decision-making in natural resource management when sufficient input data are available (Bunnefeld et al., 2017). However, uncertainties in input parameters can lead to erroneous soil erosion estimates for wider regions (Benavidez et al., 2018).

3.4.1 | Commonly used soil erosion factors as model input

This review discussed six erosion assessment methodologies in RVLB studies, with USLE and RUSLE being the most commonly used models. Additionally, key methodologies are identified for determining soil erosion factors, which are highly variable due to regional terrain, geology, soil, land use, and management parameters. The studies in the RVLB show significant differences in empirical models (USLE, RUSLE, and InVEST-SDR) input factor values within the same watershed. For example, the *K*-factor value in the Gidabo watershed varies significantly, using the same method for estimating topsoil, sand, silt, clay, and organic carbon (Guduru & Jilo, 2023). Moreover, the LS value also varies depending on the estimating methods used. These variations underscore the complexity of accurately assessing soil erosion and highlight the importance of selecting appropriate methodologies tailored to specific regional conditions.

Most studies in the RVLB use long-term rainfall data and the Hurni (1985) equation for the *R*-factor (Ali & Hagos,

2016; Asmamaw et al., 2021; Meshesha et al., 2012; Tadesse & Tefera, 2021; Wolka et al., 2015). The *K*-factor is estimated using soil color; percentage of silt, clay, sand, and organic carbon; or measured organic matter and soil permeability. Additionally, *C*-value estimation is done using literature from Ethiopia in different watersheds and basins. Moreover, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) method is used for *C*-value estimation (Wolka et al., 2015).

In RVLB, the estimated *R*-factor in most studies (16) used long-term (over 30 years) rainfall data and the Hurni (1985) equation. Two studies used the Kaltenrieder's (2007) equation. Concerning the *K*-factor, there are diverse approaches used to estimate values. Eleven studies adopted soil color to derive the *K*-factor as suggested by Hurni (1985) for Ethiopian conditions. Four studies adopted the method of estimating the *K* value from the percentage of silt, clay, sand, and organic carbon, which was developed by Wischmeier and Smith (1978). The other two studies adopted the Wischmeier and Smith's (1978) method, which used measured organic matter and soil permeability. These diverse approaches highlight the variability and adaptation of methodologies to regional conditions.

Again, in the basin, concerning *C*-value estimation, 11 studies used different literature that was conducted in Ethiopia in various watersheds and basins. Three studies used the NDVI method (Arekhi et al., 2012; Durigon et al., 2014; Park et al., 2005). Regarding *P*-factor estimation, the different studies used different methods. Most of the studies used the method proposed by Wischmeier and Smith (1978) for agricultural lands (*C*-factor range: 0.1–0.5), for slopes 0%–100%, and a *C*-factor of 1 for non-agricultural lands.

P-factor estimation often uses a value of 1 for various sites. The LS factor is derived from digital elevation model (DEM) using a standard GIS-based approach. Sediment yield studies frequently use the SWAT model with a 30 m by 30 m spatial resolution DEM, impacting sediment export study accuracy (Ghaffari, 2011). Due to a lack of calibrated values for specific sites, a *P*-factor value of 1 is commonly used at watershed scales.

The LS factor in most RVLB studies is derived from DEM using a standard GIS-based approach (Desmet & Govers, 1996). These diverse methodologies highlight the complexity and variability in assessing soil erosion and sedimentation across different regions.

4 | SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Soil erosion is a global issue threatening human livelihoods and civilization. Factors contributing to high soil loss include climate, slope, soil characteristics, surface cover, and land management practices. Land misuse, deforestation, and overgrazing cause severe erosion and excessive sediment yield. Additionally, population pressure

accelerates erosion processes by utilizing marginal lands and steep slopes.

This review compiles and analyzes previous research findings on the rate of soil erosion and sedimentation in the RVLB, focusing on the causes, rates, impacts, and methods used to estimate these factors. We collected and analyzed various studies from the internet, filtering highly related ones with the title “Soil erosion, sediment yield, RVLB, soil erosion rate.” The studies were analyzed based on subtitles such as the rate of erosion and sediment yield, the causes of erosion, its impacts, and the methods used to estimate soil loss.

Most studies on soil erosion in the RVLB reveal that land use and land cover changes, particularly the conversion of vegetation and woodland into cultivation and settlements, are the primary causes. Additionally, steep slopes also contribute to soil erosion.

The study reviewed soil erosion and sediment yield rates in the RVLB, focusing on watersheds and subbasins. In 95% of the studies, the mean annual soil loss rate was higher than the mean soil loss rate of the country. The mean annual soil loss rate of the studies was 28.44 t/ha/year, which is higher than Ethiopia’s (16.5 t/ha/year) and RVLB’s (15.8 t/ha/year) rates. The mean sediment yield rate was 5.9 t/ha/year.

Most studies have not explored the impact of soil erosion on crop production, but some suggest it threatens crop production and land productivity. On the other hand, the studies indicate that soil erosion impacts lake sedimentation in all RVLB lakes. For instance, in some cases, sediment exports increase Lake Hawassa water levels and lead to the disappearance of Lake Cheleleka. In the Lake Ziway watershed, sediment from the Meki and Katar rivers enters the lake, causing significant changes in water levels.

To sum up, the RVLB faces a significant issue of soil erosion and sediment yield, which threatens the survival of its lakes and land productivity. Urgent action is needed. Soil loss estimation methods vary due to the heterogeneity of landscapes and farming systems used in erosion assessments. Erosion model users in Ethiopia must be cautious about site-specific sensitivity and expected errors due to unreliable parameter values. To obtain consistent soil loss values, it is essential to calibrate and refine input parameters under specific conditions and compare methods with actual measurements. Future studies should investigate soil loss rate contradictions within a watershed and use accurate data for modeling.

5 | THE STATE OF THE ART, GAPS, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Current findings are as follows:

- thirty-two studies (2008–2023) identify land use changes (e.g., conversion to cultivation and settlements), steep slopes, poor conservation practices, and high rainfall as primary drivers of soil erosion;
- mean annual soil loss rate in the basin is 28.44 t/ha/year (higher than the national average of 16.5 t/ha/year and RVLB average of 15.8 t/ha/year);
- assessment methodologies used are USLE, RUSLE, SWAT, InVEST-SDR, OBIA, and FM;
- impacts include severe effects on crop production, hydrological efficiency, and lake sedimentation.

Gaps are as follows:

- methodological inconsistencies in input parameters for USLE and RUSLE models;
- limited studies on the direct impacts of soil erosion on crop production and economic losses;
- underrepresented research on gully erosion dynamics and sediment yield;
- the scarcity of high-resolution and accurate data hampers effective modeling.

Future directions are as follows

- integrate high-resolution spatial and temporal datasets to refine model inputs;
- employ advanced GIS-based models and machine learning techniques for better erosion predictions;
- conduct detailed studies on the socioeconomic and ecological impacts of soil erosion;
- policy recommendations should focus on land use planning and conservation measures;
- longitudinal studies on trends and conservation practice effectiveness.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Degefu Dogiso: Conceptualization; formal analysis; investigation; methodology; writing—original draft. **Alemayehu Muluneh:** Conceptualization; formal analysis; supervision; writing—review and editing. **Abiot Ketema:** Supervision; writing—review and editing.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We sincerely thank the Ethiopian Rift Valley Lakes Basin Authority for providing valuable information on the Rift Valley Lakes Basin.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data supporting this review study are derived from previously reported studies that have been referenced and cited.

ORCID

Degefu Dogiso <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-0285-8844>

Alemayehu Muluneh <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7192-7965>

Abiot Ketema <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5986-6245>

REFERENCES

- Aga, A. O., Chane, B., & Melesse, A. M. (2018). Soil erosion modelling and risk assessment in data scarce rift valley lake regions, Ethiopia. *Water*, 10(11), 1684. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10111684>
- Aga, A. O., Melesse, A. M., & Chane, B. (2018). Estimating the sediment flux and budget for a data limited rift valley lake in Ethiopia. *Hydrology*, 6(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology6010001>
- Aksoy, H., Mahe, G., & Meddi, M. (2019). Modeling and practice of erosion and sediment transport under change. *Water*, 11(8), 1665. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11081665>
- Ali, S. A., & Hagos, H. (2016). Estimation of soil erosion using USLE and GIS in Awassa Catchment, Rift valley, Central Ethiopia. *Geoderma Regional*, 7(2), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2016.03.005>
- Arekhi, S., Darvishi, A., Shabani, A., Fathizad, H., & Ahmadai Abchin, S. (2012). Mapping soil erosion and sediment yield susceptibility using RUSLE, remote sensing and GIS (Case study: Cham Gardalan Watershed, Iran). *Journal of Environmental Biology*, 6(1), 109–124.
- Asmamaw, L., Mohammed, A., & Mathias, T. (2021). Predicting soil erosion by water: RUSLE application for soil conservation planning in Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Environmental Engineering & Management Journal*, 20(9), 1521–1534.
- Ayalew, A. D., Wagner, P. D., Tigabu, T. B., Sahlu, D., & Fohrer, N. (2023). Hydrological responses to land use and land cover change and climate dynamics in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, Ethiopia. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 14(8), 2788–2807. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2023.138>
- Ayele, M. A., & Gebremariam, B. (2020). Evaluation of spatial and temporal variability of sediment yield on Bilate Watershed, Rift Valley Lake Basin, Ethiopia. *Journal of Water Resources and Ocean Science*, 9(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.wros.20200901.12>
- Ayele, M. A., Lohani, T. K., Mirani, K. B., Edamo, M. L., & Ayalew, A. T. (2022). Simulating sediment yield by SWAT and optimizing the parameters using SUFI-2 in Bilate river of Lake Abaya in Ethiopia. *World Journal of Engineering*, 20(4), 681–689. <https://doi.org/10.1108/WJE-07-2021-0449>
- Bekele, B. (2023). Soil erosion and sediment export in Berta watershed using GIS and USLE model in Central Rift Valley Basin, Ethiopia: Implications for sustainable natural resources management. *Ecology*, 12(1), 13–26.
- Bekele, B., & Gemi, Y. (2021). Soil erosion risk and sediment yield assessment with universal soil loss equation and GIS: In Dijo watershed, Rift valley Basin of Ethiopia. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 7(1), 273–291. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-01017-z>
- Belay, M., & Bewket, W. (2012). Assessment of gully erosion and practices for its control in north-western highlands of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 69(5), 714–728. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2012.702478>
- Benavidez, R., Jackson, B., Maxwell, D., & Norton, K. (2018). A review of the (Revised) Universal Soil Loss Equation (R) USLE: With a view to increasing its global applicability and improving soil loss estimates. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 22(11), 6059–6086. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-22-6059-2018>
- Bhattacharyya, R., Ghosh, B. N., Mishra, P. K., Mandal, B., Rao, C. S., Sarkar, D., Das, K., Anil, K., Lalitha, M., Hati, K., & Franzluebbers, A. J. (2015). Soil degradation in India: Challenges and potential solutions. *Sustainability*, 7(4), 3528–3570. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7043528>
- Boakye, E., Anyemedu, F. O. K., Donkor, E. A., & Quaye-Ballard, J. A. (2020). Spatial distribution of soil erosion and sediment yield in the Pra River Basin. *SN Applied Sciences*, 2(3), 320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-2129-1>
- Bunnefeld, N., Nicholson, E., & Milner-Gulland, E. J. (Eds.). (2017). *Decision-making in conservation and natural resource management: Models for interdisciplinary approaches* (Vol. 22). Cambridge University Press.
- Bunta, A., & Abate, B. (2021). Runoff and sediment yield modeling of Meki River watershed using SWAT model in Rift Valley lakes basin, Ethiopia. *American Journal of Civil Engineering*, 9(5), 155. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ajce.20210905.12>
- Chalise, D., Kumar, L., Shriwastav, C. P., & Lamichhane, S. (2018). Spatial assessment of soil erosion in a hilly watershed of Western Nepal. *Environmental Earth Sciences*, 77, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665-018-7842-3>
- Dananto, M., Aga, A. O., Yohannes, P., & Shura, L. (2022). Assessing the water-resources potential and soil erosion hotspot areas for sustainable land management in the Gidabo Watershed, Rift Valley Lake basin of Ethiopia. *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5262. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095262>
- Degife, A., Worku, H., & Gizaw, S. (2021). Environmental implications of soil erosion and sediment yield in Lake Hawassa watershed, south-central Ethiopia. *Environmental Systems Research*, 10, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-021-00232-6>
- Desalegn, A. T., Helsebo, T. L., & Bikiko, S. S. (2022). Soil loss estimation by using Gis And Rusle approaches in South Ethiopia, Northern-Bilate (Boyo Lake Area) Watershed. *Uttar Pradesh Journal of Zoology*, 43(11), 24–37. <https://doi.org/10.56557/upjz/2022/v43i113046>
- Desmet, P. J. J., & Govers, G. (1996). A GIS procedure for automatically calculating the USLE LS factor on topographically complex landscape units. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 51(5), 427–433.
- Durigon, V. L., Carvalho, D. F., Antunes, M. A. H., Oliveira, P. T. S., & Fernandes, M. M. (2014). NDVI time series for monitoring RUSLE cover management factor in a tropical watershed. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 35(2), 441–453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2013.871081>
- Elias, E., Seifu, W., Tesfaye, B., & Girmay, W. (2019). Impact of land use/cover changes on the lake ecosystem of Ethiopia's Central Rift Valley. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 5(1), Article 1595876.
- Fenta, A. A., Tsunekawa, A., Haregeweyn, N., Poesen, J., Tsubo, M., Borrelli, P., Panagos, P., Vanmaercke, M., Broeckx, J., Yasuda, H., Kawai, T., & Kurosaki, Y. (2020). Land susceptibility to water and wind erosion risks in the East Africa region. *Science of the Total Environment*, 703, 135016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.135016>

- Fenta, A. A., Tsunekawa, A., Haregeweyn, N., Tsubo, M., Yasuda, H., Kawai, T., Ebabu, K., Berihun, M. L., Belay, A. S., & Sultan, D. (2021). Agroecology-based soil erosion assessment for better conservation planning in Ethiopian river basins. *Environmental Research*, *195*, 110786. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.110786>
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (1986). *Ethiopian highlands reclamation study: Final report* (Vol. 1, AG:UTF/ETH/037/ETH). Food and Agriculture Organization.
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (2015). *Status of the world's soil resources: Regional assessment of soil changes in Africa south of the Sahara*. Food and Agriculture Organization. <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/385242/>
- Gadisa, N., & Midega, T. (2021). Soil and water conservation measures in Ethiopia: Importance and adoption challenges. *World Journal of Agricultural & Soil Science*, *6*(3), 2021.
- Gadissa, T., Nyadawa, M., Behulu, F., & Mutua, B. (2018). The effect of climate change on loss of lake volume: Case of sedimentation in Central Rift Valley Basin, Ethiopia. *Hydrology*, *5*(4), 67. <https://doi.org/10.3390/hydrology5040067>
- Gebre, A. M., Belete, M. D., & Belayneh, M. Z. (2023). Object-based image analysis (OBIA)-based gully erosion dynamics, sediment loading rate and sediment yield study in Lake Hawassa Sub-basin, Ethiopia. *Natural Resource Modeling*, *36*(3), e12368. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12368>
- Gelagay, H. S., & Minale, A. S. (2016). Soil loss estimation using GIS and remote sensing techniques: A case of Koga watershed, Northwestern Ethiopia. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, *4*(2), 126–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2016.01.002>
- Ghaffari, G. (2011). The impact of DEM resolution on runoff and sediment modelling results. *Research Journal of Environmental Sciences*, *5*(8), 691.
- Girma, R., & Gebre, E. (2020). Spatial modeling of erosion hotspots using GIS-RUSLE interface in Omo-Gibe river basin, Southern Ethiopia: Implication for soil and water conservation planning. *Environmental Systems Research*, *9*(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-020-00180-7>
- Guduru, J. U., & Jilo, N. B. (2023). Assessment of rainfall-induced soil erosion rate and severity analysis for prioritization of conservation measures using RUSLE and Multi-Criteria Evaluations Technique at Gidabo watershed, Rift Valley Basin, Ethiopia. *Ecohydrology & Hydrobiology*, *23*(1), 30–47.
- Hassen, G., & Bantider, A. (2020). Assessment of drivers and dynamics of gully erosion in case of Tabota Koromo and Koromo Danshe watersheds, South Central Ethiopia. *Geoenvironmental Disasters*, *7*(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40677-019-0138-4>
- Hoogenboom, P. E. (2013). *Sediment yield by gully erosion in a sub catchment of the Awassa watershed, Ethiopia* [Master's thesis, Utrecht University]. UU Theses Repository.
- Hurni, H. (1985). Erosion–productivity–conservation systems in Ethiopia. In P. Sentis (Ed.), *Soil Conservation and Productivity: Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Soil Conservation* (pp. 654–674). Scientific Research.
- Hurni, H. (1988). Degradation and conservation of the resources in the Ethiopian highlands. *Mountain Research and Development*, *8*, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3673438>
- Kalsido, T., & Berhanu, B. (2020). Impact of land-use changes on sediment load and capacity reduction of Lake Ziway, Ethiopia. *Natural Resources*, *11*(11), 530–542. <https://doi.org/10.4236/nr.2020.1111031>
- Kaltenrieder, J. (2007). *Adaptation and validation of the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE) for the Ethiopian-Eritrean highlands* [Master's thesis, Geographisches Institut, University of Bern].
- Kebede, Y. S., Endalamaw, N. T., Sinshaw, B. G., & Atinkut, H. B. (2021). Modeling soil erosion using RUSLE and GIS at watershed level in the upper beles, Ethiopia. *Environmental Challenges*, *2*, 100009. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2020.100009>
- Ketema, A., & Dwarakish, G. S. (2020). Prioritization of sub-watersheds for conservation measures based on soil loss rate in Tikur Wuha watershed, Ethiopia. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, *13*(19), 1051. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-020-06054-7>
- Kidane, M., Bezie, A., Kesete, N., & Tolessa, T. (2019). The impact of land use and land cover (LULC) dynamics on soil erosion and sediment yield in Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, *5*(12), e02981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02981>
- Mamedov, A. I., & Levy, G. J. (2019). Soil erosion–runoff relations on cultivated land: Insights from laboratory studies. *European Journal of Soil Science*, *70*(3), 686–696. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.12759>
- Mariye, M., Mariyo, M., Changming, Y., Teffera, Z. L., & Weldegebrail, B. (2022). Effects of land use and land cover change on soil erosion potential in Berhe district: A case study of Legedadi watershed, Ethiopia. *International Journal of River Basin Management*, *20*(1), 79–91. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15715124.2020.1767636>
- Masha, M., Yirgu, T., & Debele, M. (2021). Impacts of land cover and greenness change on soil loss and erosion risk in Damota area districts, southern Ethiopia. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, *2021*(1), 9148138.
- Mathewos, M., Tsegaye, M., & Wondrade, N. (2023). Soil erosion variations along land use and land cover dynamics in Matenchose watershed, Rift Valley Basin, Southern Ethiopia. *Natural Resource Modeling*, *36*(4), e12379. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12379>
- Mengie, M. A., Hagos, Y. G., Malede, D. A., & Andualem, T. G. (2022). Assessment of soil loss rate using GIS–RUSLE interface in Tashat Watershed, Northwestern Ethiopia. *Journal of Sedimentary Environments*, *7*(3), 617–631. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43217-022-00112-8>
- Meshesha, D. T., Tsunekawa, A., Tsubo, M., & Haregeweyn, N. (2012). Dynamics and hotspots of soil erosion and management scenarios of the Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Sediment Research*, *27*(1), 84–99. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-6279\(12\)60018-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-6279(12)60018-3)
- Ministry of Water and Energy (MoWE). (2009). *Rift Valley Lakes Basin integrated resources development master plan study project report Addis Ababa* (Vol. 2). Unpublished.
- Moges, A., & Holden, N. M. (2008). Estimating the rate and consequences of gully development, a case study of Umbulo catchment in southern Ethiopia. *Land Degradation & Development*, *19*(5), 574–586.
- Moussa, A. M. A. (2019). Assessment of sediment deposition in Aswan high dam reservoir during 50 years (1964–2014). In A. Negm & S. Abdel-Fattah (Eds.), *Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam versus Aswan High Dam: A view from Egypt* (pp. 233–253). Springer.
- Negese, A. (2021). Impacts of land use and land cover change on soil erosion and hydrological responses in Ethiopia. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, *2021*(1), 6669438.
- Nigusie, A., & Dananto, M. (2021). Soil loss mapping and severity analysis by using Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) modeling: A case study of Dijo River Watershed, Central Rift Valley

- Basin of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Scientific and Technical Research in Engineering*, 6(4), 21–34.
- Onet, A., Dincă, L. C., Grenni, P., Laslo, V., Teusdea, A. C., Vasile, D. L., Enescu, R. E., & Crisan, V. E. (2019). Biological indicators for evaluating soil quality improvement in a soil degraded by erosion processes. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, 19, 2393–2404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11368-018-02236-9>
- Palmieri, A., Shah, F., & Dinar, A. (2001). Economics of reservoir sedimentation and sustainable management of dams. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 61(2), 149–163. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jema.2000.0392>
- Panagos, P., Borrelli, P., Meusburger, K., Alewell, C., Lugato, E., & Montanarella, L. (2015). Estimating the soil erosion cover-management factor at the European scale. *Land Use Policy*, 48, 38–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2015.05.021>
- Pandit, R., Scholes, R., Montanarella, L., Brainich, A., Barger, N., ten Brink, B., & Willemsen, L. (2018). *Summary for policymakers of the assessment report on land degradation and restoration*. Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES).
- Park, C. S., Jung, Y. S., Joo, J. H., & Lee, J. T. (2005). Best management practices reducing soil loss in the saprolite piled upland in Hongcheon highland. *Korean Journal of Soil Science and Fertilizer*, 38(3), 119–126.
- Rodrigo Comino, J., Brings, C., Lassu, T., Iserloh, T., Senciales, J. M., Martínez Murillo, J. F., Ruiz Sinoga, J. D., Seeger, M., & Ries, J. B. (2015). Rainfall and human activity impacts on soil losses and rill erosion in vineyards (Ruwer Valley, Germany). *Solid Earth*, 6(3), 823–837. <https://doi.org/10.5194/se-6-823-2015>
- Sanogo, K., Zemadim, B., & Kizito, F. (2021). *Vulnerability of landscape patterns from a multidisciplinary approach based on remote sensing and GIS in two agroecologies of Mali*. International Institute of Tropical Agriculture.
- Sime, C. H., & Abebe, W. T. (2022). Sediment yield modeling and mapping of the spatial distribution of soil erosion-prone areas. *Applied and Environmental Soil Science*, 2022(1), 4291699.
- Tadese, S., Soromessa, T., & Bekele, T. (2021). Analysis of the current and future prediction of land use/land cover change using remote sensing and the CA-Markov model in Majang forest biosphere reserves of Gambella, Southwestern Ethiopia. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2021(1), 6685045.
- Tadesse, T. B., & Tefera, S. A. (2021). Comparing potential risk of soil erosion using RUSLE and MCDA techniques in Central Ethiopia. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 7(3), 1713–1725. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00881-z>
- Tamire, C., Elias, E., & Argaw, M. (2022). Spatiotemporal dynamics of soil loss and sediment export in Upper Bilate River Catchment (UBRC), Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 8(11), e11220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11220>
- Taye, G., Teklesilassie, T., Teka, D., & Kassa, H. (2023). Assessment of soil erosion hazard and its relation to land use land cover changes: Case study from alage watershed, central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 9(8), e18648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18648>
- Toma, M. B., Belete, M. D., & Ulsido, M. D. (2023). Hydrological components and sediment yield response to land use land cover change in the Ajora-Woybo watershed of Omo-Gibe basin, Ethiopia. *Air, Soil and Water Research*, 16, 11786221221150186. <https://doi.org/10.1177/11786221221150186>
- Tsegaye, L., & Bharti, R. (2021). Soil erosion and sediment yield assessment using RUSLE and GIS-based approach in Anjeb watershed, Northwest Ethiopia. *SN Applied Sciences*, 3, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04564-x>
- Tully, K., Sullivan, C., Weil, R., & Sanchez, P. (2015). The state of soil degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa: Baselines, trajectories, and solutions. *Sustainability*, 7(6), 6523–6552. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su7066523>
- Vigiak, O., Borselli, L., Newham, L. T. H., McInnes, J., & Roberts, A. M. (2012). Comparison of conceptual landscape metrics to define hillslope-scale sediment delivery ratio. *Geomorphology*, 138(1), 74–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2011.08.026>
- Welde, K. (2016). Identification and prioritization of subwatersheds for land and water management in Tekeze dam watershed, Northern Ethiopia. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 4(1), 30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswcr.2016.02.006>
- Weldu Woldemariam, G., & Edo Harka, A. (2020). Effect of land use and land cover change on soil erosion in erer sub-basin, Northeast Wabi Shebelle Basin, Ethiopia. *Land*, 9(4), 111. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land9040111>
- Wischmeier, W. H., & Smith, D. D. (1978). *Predicting rainfall erosion losses: A guide to conservation planning* (No. 537). Department of Agriculture, Science and Education Administration.
- Woldesenbet, A. B., Wudmatas, S. D., Denboba, M. A., & Gebremariam, A. G. (2020). Enset-based land use land cover change detection and its impact on soil erosion in Meki river watershed, Western Lake Ziway Sub-Basin, Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Environmental Systems Research*, 9, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-020-00198-x>
- Wolka, K., Tadesse, H., Garedew, E., & Yimer, F. (2015). Soil erosion risk assessment in the Chaleleka wetland watershed, Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Environmental Systems Research*, 4, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40068-015-0030-5>
- Wondrade, N. (2023). Integrated use of GIS, RS and USLE model for LULC change analysis and soil erosion risk mapping in the Lake Hawassa Watershed, Southern Ethiopia. *Geocarto International*, 38(1), 2210106. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2023.2210106>
- Yazie, T., Mekonnen, M., Derebe, A., & Melese, T. (2020). Investigating long year gully erosion and its impacts on soil loss, land competition and crop yield reduction, north-west Ethiopia. *Authorea*. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.158471481.14850106>
- Yirgu, T. (2022). Assessment of soil erosion hazard and factors affecting farmers' adoption of soil and water management measure: A case study from Upper Domba Watershed, Southern Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 8(6), e09536. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09536>
- Zegeye, A. D., Amare, S. D., Tilahun, S. A., Langendoen, E. J., Dagnaw, D. C., Guzman, C. D., ... Steenhuis, T. S. (2014). Gully development processes in the Ethiopian Highlands. In *Proceedings of the second International Conference on the advancements in science and technology (ICAST)*, (pp. 220–229). Bahir Dar University.

How to cite this article: Dogiso, D., Muluneh, A., & Ketema, A. (2025). Assessment of soil erosion and sedimentation dynamics in the Rift Valley Lakes Basin, Ethiopia. *Agrosystems, Geosciences & Environment*, 8, e70062. <https://doi.org/10.1002/agg2.70062>